

METHODOLOGY FOR IMPROVING THE TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL TRAINING OF NATIONAL WRESTLERS

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Abstract: this article presents the scientific methodological foundations of improving the technique and tactics of national wrestlers

Keywords: technical training, general basics of Performing Technical actions, ways to improve the technical skills of The Wrestler, goals and objectives of tactical training, tactics of preparing offensive actions, tactics of drawing up a competition, tactics of participating in competitions.

МЕТОДИКА СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ТЕХНИКО- ТАКТИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ БОРЦОВ

Аннотация: в данной статье представлены научно-методические основы совершенствования техники и тактики национальных борцов.

Ключевые слова: техническая подготовка, общие основы выполнения технических действий, пути совершенствования технического мастерства борца, цели и задачи тактической подготовки, тактика подготовки наступательных действий, тактика оформления соревнования, тактика участия в соревнованиях.

INTRODUCTION

Technical training the technical training of the fight is characterized by the degree of occupancy of the system of actions by the athlete, which ensures the achievement of high sporting results. The general and special technical training of the wrestler is distinguished. General technical training is aimed at acquiring various movement skills and skills in auxiliary sports, special technical training is aimed at achieving technical skills in sports wrestling. In sports wrestling, technical training is aimed at solving a number of complex tasks:

- to increase the efficiency of using the maximum voltage;
- to save the operating voltage;
- to increase the speed, accuracy of movement in conditions of changing competition activities.

The improvement of sports techniques is carried out during the many years of training of wrestlers, and it is aimed at improving technical skills in the selected type of wrestling. Technical skill is understood as the perfect mastery of the most rational movement technique in the conditions of a sharp Sports fight.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ways to improve the technical skill of a wrestler the richer the reserve of technical actions of a wrestler, the greater the skill he can apply them, the higher his

technical skill. Wrestling techniques are the basis of a wrestler's skill and in many ways determine his capabilities. There are dozens of methods and their options in the fight. However, this does not mean that the wrestler should know them all perfectly. As the athlete acquires more new and new methods, counter-methods and defenses, part of the methods that meet his particular characteristics and habits and are successfully performed by him are included in the plan for the purpose of further improvement. Versatile technical training of a wrestler is one of the important requirements for the modern level of development of various sports. When choosing technical actions for a solid occupation, the following rules should be followed:

- in the current competition rules, which one technical action to master those technical actions that are considered successful;
- to master the options for methods, counter-methods and defenses that best respond to the individual characteristics of the athlete from within all types of techniques;
- taking into account the characteristics of the skill of the main competitors and choosing technical actions that will give a good result when dealing with them;
- focusing more on technical actions that can expand the possibility of applying previously studied methods and counter-methods;
- study of combinations with the methods available in the wrestler's Reserve, as well as technical actions that can be applied in ties;
- it is necessary to train the movement technique, which has the property of solving the task of action most rationally; this is nothing more than further re-learning;
- it is necessary that the training in the methods is concentrated in the time frame, since long breaks between training sessions reduce its effect. On the other hand, it is not advisable to repeat the methods too often during one training lesson, the creation of new coordination of the Chuck is associated with overcoming the difficulty that quickly exhausts the nervous system;
- in order to avoid technical conditions arising from insufficient physical conditions, it is necessary to organize a high level of special physical training corresponding to dynamic descriptions of movements.

The purpose and objectives of tactical training is combat tactics - the use of technical, physical and volitional capabilities in accordance with Maksud in certain conditions that have arisen in order to achieve the best result in competitions. Tactical training is aimed at acquiring the necessary knowledge in the field of tactics in athletes, the formation of certain skills and knowledge in the correct conduct of sports wrestling, as well as improving tactical skills. The main goal of tactical training is to educate the athlete in the ability to properly organize and conduct sports competitions in order to achieve victory in the competition or show a higher result. In the process of mastering Sports tactics, a number of private tasks are solved.

Athlete: - it is necessary to perceive and analyze the competition situation in such a way that he is able to understand the tactical tasks arising from this situation and solve it with imagination and effort in a short time;

- he must use his strength in the competition in such a way that, in order to win over the opponent, he must be able to mobilize it to the end;

- in situations that suddenly change, he must be able to independently change the competition plan. The main tasks of tactical training:

- acquire tactical knowledge;
- acquisition of tactical skills;
- have tactical qualifications.

Tactical tools include the movements of athletes, represented by a strictly defined movement structure and the level of physical qualities necessary for their manifestation. Tactics in wrestling are made up of three main sections:

- tactics of preparing offensive actions;
- contest formation tactics;
- tactics of participation in competitions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All methods of tactical preparation for the implementation of technical methods can participate in a state of sophistication independent, but harmonized (that is, favorable conditions for the implementation of the method are prepared not by one, but by several methods that complement each other). Tactics of preparing offensive actions tactical training of an offensive action by a certain method should be part of a complex method. In this, it is performed continuously by the method of attack. Particular attention should be paid to the moment of transition from a deceptive action (tactical preparation of personally attacking execution) to the final action of a complex offensive action. It is necessary to choose the methods of tactical training that are most expedient to various attack methods. To this end, wrestlers receive the following assignment after familiarizing themselves with the approximation: independently choosing methods of tactical training for a particular method and combining them with methods of attack. In improving complex attack movements, the pedagogical process is aimed at raising new skills.

The tactics of drawing up the competition the tactics of Sports Wrestling are regularly developing in accordance with the development of technology, the rules of the competition and the changes in the arbitration system. Currently, a tactic in which a standing attack is performed by a wrestler is preferred. In this case, even if he has not organized any attacks that are judged by points, while his opponent is only protected bulsa, he is given an advantage, while the opponent receives a warning for sluggishness. The wrestler must have a large number of simple cell movements, various methods of tactical training in his fund to apply the tactics of non-stop attacks. In addition, such a tactic assumes a high degree of endurance. At the same time it is relatively calm and can be replaced by periods of excitation of the opponent. In this, the wrestler must be ready to repel the opponent's attack.

The tactics of participation in competitions the tactics of holding the entire competition are determined after the draw, that is, after the composition of the

opponents is determined and the pairs of soon-to-be-held contests are formed. After that, the purpose of each meeting is determined in order to roughly know the number of periods (meetings) that must be passed in order to take a certain place in the competitions, which are held by the exit after two sessions. It is necessary to determine which contests the wrestler should win “pure”, with a clear advantage, which should be won by points. In order to behave tactically correctly, it is necessary to assess the state of the tournament and the state of the opponent at the end of each round. To do this, it is necessary to carry out a schedule of competitions for your own weight category. Intelligence in the continuation of the competition will help to obtain more accurate information about the opponent's preparation. Intelligence is mainly conducted at the beginning of the competition and is aimed at determining what methods the opponent is using, what kind of counterattack he is launching, the equipment of his tactical training, the speed, strength and endurance of the reaction. To do this, it is possible to apply a challenge to the opponent by deliberately creating favorable conditions for performing one way or another of the attack. In this case, it is necessary to be prepared for protection and to organize a counterattack. Deceptive attacks can be used in various ways to determine the opponent's response reaction, but it is necessary to be prepared to defend against his counterattacks at the same time. Maneuvering serves to determine the opponent's attack methods (retreat from the opponent and approach him, move in his atorph, etc.k.).

Changing the position in the carpet area, in its center or on the edge can serve as an intelligence goal. It allows you to determine where the opponent prefers to fight, how to attack him or how to defend against him. It is not necessary to collect data in a new way every time, it is necessary to use all known information from meetings with the same opponent first, as well as have a paper on the preparation of possible opponents.

In addition to intelligence, another of the important tactical actions was considered to be the concealment of intent. It is a tactical move of the wrestler, in which the wrestler hides his true intent from him by obstructing the opponent's reconnaissance in the wrestling process. Proper concealment depends on the personal discovery of the wrestler. Accelerated; with severe breathing and slowness of movements, it is possible to demonstrate severe exhaustion and at the same time perform a quick and sharp attack at the competition, ready to “explode”. With an empty opponent, it is necessary to try to win by secondary methods without applying His “Royal” methods.

CONCLUSION

Wrestlers and future physical education teacher, coach and athletes provide practical assistance to form clear concepts and imaginations in the training of athletes with excellent technical, tactical, mental volitional and physical training, incorporating in their content common, tactical, technical and special training methods and Means.

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